

SUHAMK COARAB PROJECT ANALYSIS REPORT

‘Strengthening the Qualitative Criteria
for the Researcher Assessment at
Häme University of Applied Sciences’-
Fieldwork Analysis Report

Abstract

This report presents the analysis and findings of the fieldwork conducted as part of the SuHAMK CoARAb project between January-March 2025. This report contains a detailed overview of the fieldwork conducted, participant data, an overview of the analysis and a wider discussion of the findings.

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Introduction

SuHAMK CoARAb Project

This document has been created as part of the SuHAMK CoARAb project at Häme University of Applied Sciences. The SuHAMK CoARAb project is part of the CoARA Cascade Boost Funding and funded by the European Union.

This 1-year EU funded project aims to develop new effective qualitative researcher evaluation criteria which will be mapped into HAMK's existing principal research scientist evaluation processes. The new qualitative researcher evaluation criteria support the recognition of diverse researcher skills and different researcher career paths, enhances HAMK's research quality and promotes transparency and accountability in the researcher evaluation processes. Strong collaboration with HAMK's principal research scientists, principal research scientist supervisors, the researcher evaluation team and other relevant HAMK personnel have helped identify the new qualitative evaluation criteria in this document. A new sustainable evaluation framework will be developed around these new criteria and comprehensive training on their active utilization will be provided to relevant HAMK personnel.

Overview of Fieldwork

Over 80% of relevant HAMK personnel have participated in the fieldwork. The fieldwork primarily included existing HAMK Principal Research Scientists, Principal Research Scientist supervisors, and the researcher evaluation team from all HAMK's research departments, BIO, TECH, EDU and SOCHEALTH. Other personnel, including the Vice Rector, the publication team, experts, and HR personnel also contributed.

The fieldwork included a survey, semi-structured interviews and two workshops. All of the fieldwork was completed between January-March 2025.

Participant Overview

The table below provides an overview of the participants targeted and the participants who participated in the fieldwork.

Participant Category	Participation Rate
Principal Research Scientists	
BIO	6/
TECH	10/
EDU	10/
SOCHEALTH	2/
Total	28/37
Principal Research Scientist Supervisors	
BIO	1/1

TECH	1/1
EDU	1/1
Total	3/3 (100%)
Researcher Evaluation Team	
BIO	1/1
TECH	2/2
EDU	1/1
Total	4/4 (100%)
Other Relevant Personnel	
Experts	2/2
Decision Makers	1/1
Publication Team	3/3
HR	2/2
Total	8/8 (100%)

Implementation of Fieldwork Findings

The fieldwork was conducted in stages. The findings from each phase of fieldwork informed us of the design and implementation of the subsequent fieldwork. The survey was conducted and analysed before conducting the interviews. Both workshops were conducted following the analysis of the interviews and survey.

Survey

Overview

The aim of the survey was to gain insight into the current **perceptions** and **experiences** of the researcher **evaluation process** and **evaluation criteria**. A second objective of the survey was to understand what aspects were **most valued** or deemed **most important** in relation to different researcher **evaluation criteria**.

Two separate versions of the survey were designed. **One survey** was designed for the existing **Principal Research Scientists** at HAMK. **A second survey** was designed for both the **Principal Research Scientist supervisors** and **researcher evaluation team** at HAMK. After informing relevant participants of the survey, a link to the survey was sent to all relevant participants.

Participants

The following participants participated in the survey:

Research Department	Number
Principal Research Scientists	
BIO	5
TECH	9
EDU	8
SOCHEALTH	2
Total	24/37 (64%)
Principal Research Scientist Supervisors	
BIO	1/1
TECH	1/1
EDU	1/1
Total	3/3 (100%)
Researcher Evaluation Team	
BIO	1/1
TECH	2/2
EDU	1/1
Total	4/4 (100%)

Methodology

A literature review was conducted exploring the discussions on qualitative evaluation criteria to both researcher and research evaluation processes. Previous studies and tools were explored to understand current consideration of qualitative criteria alongside the skills which are believed to be captured more successfully using qualitative criteria.

The survey questions were designed to coincide with the findings from the literature review. The participants were asked questions regarding their opinions about the importance of research impact and researcher influence.

Questions focused on understanding to what extent qualitative criteria can capture research impact, researcher influence and other key researcher skills. Opinions on the potential opportunities and challenges of using qualitative evaluation criteria were also explored.

The survey questions were made up of Likert scale questions (**completely disagree, somewhat disagree, somewhat agree, completely agree**), and open-ended questions.

Findings

An analysis of the survey results is presented below. First, an overview of the answers of the Principal Research Scientist is provided, and thereafter an overview of the Principal Research Scientist supervisors and the evaluation team is highlighted. Finally, the similarities, tensions and other important themes are discussed.

Principal Research Scientists

Research Department	Number
Principal Research Scientists	
BIO	5
TECH	9
EDU	8
SOCHEALTH	2
Total	24/37 (64%)

Years of research experience	Number	Percentage
0-5	1	4.2%
6-10	6	25.0%
11+	17	70.8%

The majority of the Principal Research Scientists (PRS) had more than 6 years of research experience.

Role of Research Impact

Research impact was considered an **important** aspect when evaluating researchers. 74% of the respondents either **completely agreed (35%)** or **somewhat agreed (39%)** with research impact being an essential component of the researcher assessment.

In the survey **research impact** was understood as the potential impact of the research itself. The quality of the research was therefore focused upon in this question.

Demonstrating and Measuring Research Impact

The respondents were asked to provide feedback on the suitability of the following criteria for measuring research impact:

- Multiple authors or research contributors,
- Use of a multidisciplinary approach (such as authors from different academic fields, inclusion of multiple academic fields in publications, presentation of research at multidisciplinary conferences etc.),
- Research conducted in collaboration with stakeholders,
- Research conducted in collaboration with diverse stakeholders,
- Demonstrated relevance of research to current local societal issues,
- Demonstrated relevance of research to current international societal issues,
- Demonstrated relevance of research in future (expected duration of research relevance),
- Demonstrated practical applicability of research in local society (applicable to local businesses, local non-profit organizations, local non-profit institutions, local policies etc.),
- Demonstrated practical applicability of research in international society (applicable to international businesses, international non-profit organizations, international government institutions etc.),
- Demonstrated practical applicability of research in UAS study units,
- Accessibility of research at all levels of society (such as academics, private business owners, policymakers, educators, ordinary citizens etc.),

Analysis of Research Impact Criteria:

The respondents were asked to comment on the list of criteria as appropriate measures for research impact.

The results of the respondents can be found below:

The following criteria were primarily ***agreed upon*** as the most relevant criteria for measuring research impact:

- **Demonstrated practical applicability of research in local society** (applicable to local businesses, local non-profit organizations, local non-profit institutions, local policies etc.). (39% completely agree, 44% somewhat agree).
- **Demonstrated practical applicability of research in international society** (applicable to international businesses, international non-profit organizations, international government institutions etc.). (39% completely agree, 35% somewhat agree).
- **Demonstrated relevance of research in future.** (35% completely agree, 39% somewhat agree).
- **Accessibility of research at all levels of society** (such as academics, private business owners, policymakers, educators, ordinary citizens etc.). (30% completely agree, 44% somewhat agree).

For the following criteria, whilst the majority of respondents did agree that these were relevant measures for research impact, these criteria were also most ***disagreed upon***:

- **Multiple authors or research contributors** (4% completely disagree, 9% disagree, 26% unsure).
- **Use of a multidisciplinary approach** (such as authors from different academic fields, inclusion of multiple academic fields in publications, presentation of research at multidisciplinary conferences etc.). (17% somewhat disagree, 22% unsure).
- **Demonstrated practical applicability of research in UAS study units,** (9% somewhat disagree, 30% unsure).
- **Research conducted in collaboration with diverse stakeholders** (4% somewhat disagree, 31% unsure).

Whilst the respondents generally agreed upon the potential criteria for measuring research impact, the multidisciplinary research, collaboration with multiple authors and/or diverse stakeholders, and the applicability of research with the study units of the education institution were the most disputed. However, these criteria were also not completely dismissed or considered as irrelevant.

In addition, whilst research impact was recognized as an important consideration in researcher evaluation, the following points were highlighted:

- The way research impact was measured was highlighted as an important consideration. The impact of some research, or research produced in certain research areas, is evidently easier to assess than in others. For example, impact assessment of projects or research which produce practical applications are easier to identify in comparison to assessing policies and shifts in social culture.

- In addition, different types of research and/or projects will produce impact on a different time scale. Research impact may only become evident in some cases over a longer period; however, this does not reduce its relevance or value.
- In relation to this, it is important to identify tools and methods for recognizing research impact in the short term as this greatly supports the career progression of many researchers.
- In addition, research career stages and overall experience heavily impact upon the visibility of impact. The **potential** impact should also be recognized and considered important. This supports the career progression of younger or early career stage researchers.

Role of Researcher influence

The role of researcher influence in the researcher evaluation was considered as important by 70% of the respondents. 35% completely agreed and 35% somewhat agreed that the influence of the researcher should be included in the researcher assessment.

The respondents were asked to provide feedback on the suitability of the following criteria for measuring researcher influence:

- Role in funding applications,
- Role in published publications or other products or formats of research (such as patents, technology, software, etc.),
- Collaboration with different academic fields in projects or research related activities,
- Collaboration with different stakeholders in projects or research related activities (such as businesses, policymakers, non-profit organizations etc.),
- Collaboration with a diverse range of people from different backgrounds,
- Collaboration with UAS study units,
- Participation in local research conferences, lectures, webinars, presentations, panels etc.,
- Participation in international conferences, lectures, webinars, presentations, panels etc.,
- Participation in research mobility programs,
- Role in teaching activities,
- Feedback on teaching activities from students and/or colleagues,
- Role in researcher supervision activities,
- Feedback on supervision activities from students and/or colleagues,
- Range of different methodological skills utilized in projects, research activities, teaching activities and supervision activities,
- Use of different formats of communication (such as articles, presentations, speeches, workshops etc.),
- Experience in communicating with different audiences (such as academic audiences, policymakers, private businesses, ordinary citizens etc.)

Analysis of Researcher Influence criteria

The respondents were asked to comment on the list of criteria as appropriate measures of researcher influence.

The results of the respondents can be found below:

The following criteria were primarily **agreed upon** as the most relevant criteria for measuring researcher influence:

- **Role in published publications or other products or formats of research** (such as patents, technology, software, etc.) (61% completely agree, 39% somewhat agree).
- **Role in funding applications** (48% completely agree, 52% somewhat agree),
- **Collaboration with different academic fields in projects or research related activities**, (43% completely agree, 57% somewhat agree).
- **Collaboration with different stakeholders in projects or research related activities** (such as businesses, policymakers, non-profit organizations etc.) (48% completely agree, 48% somewhat agree).
- **Participation in international conferences, lectures, webinars, presentations, panels etc.**, (61% completely agree, 35% somewhat agree).
- **Role in researcher supervision activities** (43% completely agree, 48% somewhat agree).
- **Experience in communicating with different audiences** (such as academic audiences, policymakers, private businesses, ordinary citizens etc.) (39% completely agreed, 39% somewhat agreed).
- **Feedback on supervision activities from students and/or colleagues** (39% completely agree, 35% somewhat agree).

- **Range of different methodological skills utilized in projects, research activities, teaching activities and supervision activities**, (39% completely agree, 35% somewhat agree).
- **Use of different formats of communication** (such as articles, presentations, speeches, workshops etc.), (35% completely agree, 44% somewhat agree),
- **Role in teaching activities** (17% completely agree, 61% somewhat agree).

For the following criteria, whilst the majority of respondents did agree that these were relevant measures of researcher influence, these criteria were also most ***disagreed upon***:

- **Participation in mobility programs** (4% completely disagree, 22% somewhat disagree),
- **Collaboration with diverse range of people from different backgrounds** (17% somewhat disagree),
- **Feedback on teaching activities from students and/or colleagues**, (17% somewhat disagree),

Similar to the results of the research impact criteria, the criteria which associate importance to teaching and UAS study units, is slightly disagreed upon. However, these criteria are considered important by the majority of the respondents, but opinions do evidently fluctuate more in comparison to the other criteria. Collaboration measured in terms of diversity was also somewhat disagreed upon, similar to the criteria of collaboration with diverse stakeholders when assessing research impact. Nevertheless, again, the majority of respondents do acknowledge their importance. Mobility programs were the most disagreed upon criteria. Further analysis on how the benefits of mobility programs can be gained through other activities, or if these benefits are viewed as important.

The respondents also highlighted that researcher influence should be understood as demonstrated years of researcher experience, alongside considerable collaborations and stakeholders and active networks.

Role of Cooperation and Collaboration

The respondents were asked to what extent the following criteria were relevant to measuring cooperation and collaboration skills:

- Participation in either funding applications or research, which has multidisciplinary involvement.
- Participation in either funding applications or research, which considers multistakeholder involvement.
- Researcher involvement with other academic institutions.
- Researcher involvement with private sector institutions.
- Researcher involvement in UAS study units.

- Researcher involvement with other societal institutions.

Analysis of Collaboration and Cooperation criteria

The results of the respondents can be found below:

The following criteria were primarily ***agreed upon*** as the most relevant criteria for measuring collaboration and cooperation for UAS researchers:

- **Researcher involvement with other academic institutions** (61% completely agreed, 39% somewhat agreed),
- **Participation in either funding applications or research, which has multidisciplinary involvement** (44% completely agreed, 48% somewhat agreed),
- **Participation in either funding applications or research, which considers multistakeholder involvement** (44% completely agreed, 48% somewhat agreed),

For the following criteria, whilst the majority of respondents did agree that these were relevant when measuring collaboration and cooperation skills of UAS researchers, these criteria were also most ***disagreed upon***:

- **Researcher involvement with private sector institutions** (4% somewhat disagree, 13% unsure),
- **Researcher involvement in UAS study units** (4% somewhat disagree, 13% unsure),
- **Researcher involvement with other societal institutions** (9% somewhat disagree, 4% unsure),

However, primarily all of these criteria were reorganized as relevant indicators for collaboration and cooperation skills in UAS researchers.

The respondents also made the following comments:

- For UAS researchers, practical goals, objectives, the usefulness of the research, and the impact of the results in renewing working life, producing innovations, and thereby enabling a good life should be emphasized. Academic research perspective should not be heavily emphasized.
- Quantitative criteria, such as the number of researchers involved, should be replaced by measuring the actual quality of the research. Nevertheless, how quality can be fairly, and objectively analysed remains unclear.
- Different research contexts and fields will alter the effectiveness of different criteria. The relevance and appropriateness of the criteria in terms of the study context and field need to always be considered.
- It is important to acknowledge that influence does not expand from working with different researchers but going outside of the researchers' own discipline and working with a variety of researchers from different academic institutions is needed.
- Involvement of different stakeholders from both the business industry and NGO organizations in publications increases participation and commitment to common goals and missions.
- Other criteria which highlight researcher influence are doctoral thesis examinations, being the opponent in doctoral defense, being an external reviewer in project applications and grants, being an editor of a journal or scientific committee, being an organizer of a conference, seminar, workshop or part of the organizing committee, etc.
- Different criteria highlighting researcher expertise need to be considered for different levels of a researcher's career. The tasks and position alter depending on the career.
- Different awards and prizes are also good indicators of influence.

Opinions and Comments on: Communication Skills, Marketing Skills, Cooperation Skills, Flexibility, and Strategic Planning

The respondents were also asked to comment and provide feedback on how, in their opinion, researchers could demonstrate skills in **effective communication**, their ability to **market ideas, research and projects**, their ability to **learn and cooperate**, their ability to **be flexible with ideas and respond to new research and findings**, ability to **write cohesive strategies and plans**. Below is an overview of the feedback provided by the respondents:

Effective Communication Skills:

The respondents perceived that a researcher can practically demonstrate effective communication skills through **collaborative research** (the involvement of multiple authors, partners, researchers, and stakeholders), experience communicating and/or presenting to **different audiences** (students, business industry stakeholders,

academic researchers, etc.), having experience communicating using **different industry languages** (adapting communication style and content when collaborating or networking with different types of stakeholders from different types of industries), **participation and presence in different events and social media channels** (being actively involved in activities and utilizing different media platforms to communicate), experience in **using different mediums to communicate** (creating videos, live demonstration, presentations, webinars, teaching materials etc.).

The creation of an **e-portfolio** was suggested as a potential method for noting down all of the different demonstrations of communication skills.

One respondent also highlighted the **importance** of **honest, transparent** and **academically respectful** communication skills needed when **marketing research** and/or projects to stakeholders. Business industry stakeholders should not be misled in getting involved in projects and/or research. Thus, a balance between researcher integrity and marketing needs to be established.

Ability to market ideas, research and projects?

The majority respondents perceived that a researcher can practically demonstrate their ability to market ideas, research and projects by **receiving funding approvals and leading or participating in funding applications**. Securing or being involved in successful funding applications was noted multiple times by different researchers.

However, other suggestions focused on specific communication skills including the **ability to communicate with different industry stakeholders, activeness in networking events with relevant stakeholders**, being able to **utilize social media platforms and channels to popularize research outputs and results and gain interest and attention from key stakeholders**. Marketing skills were thus understood as a specific set of communication and research dissemination skills and being able to attract the interest of relevant stakeholders.

However, one respondent also reflected on the necessity of marketing skills for UAS researchers. For this respondent, **marketing skills were not an appropriate skill for UAS researchers** as the researchers work within an academic institution, and thus, marketing skills are not appropriate. Research was thus viewed as needing to be focused upon the **creation and enhancement of knowledge through research**, which will **consequently help the business industry** stakeholders in the short and long term. Thus, through the creation and **dissemination of knowledge**, the researcher will **positively impact upon regional business industry stakeholders** and marketing is not needed.

Ability to learn and cooperate?

The respondents perceived that a researcher can practically demonstrate their ability to learn and cooperate through **collaborative research in particular multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary collaboration, supervisory and project and/or research lead** roles and duties, demonstrated experience in **adopting different types of methods** in research and/or projects, being involved in various **different networks**, and the **adoption of new ideas and methods** and keeping up to date with changes in the field.

However, one respondent highlighted that **collaboration and cooperation** with the rest of the world is **primarily achieved through successful publication and dissemination of research**. Researchers are thus also able to work independently and should thus not be required to actively collaborate with others. The collaboration of researchers should be demonstrated through the **researcher's ability to remain up to date with research and field changes**. Thus, **on the ground awareness is key**.

Ability to be flexible with ideas and respond to new research and findings?

The respondents perceived that a researcher can practically demonstrate their ability to be flexible with ideas and respond to new research and findings through **continued activeness in projects, collaborations and funding approvals, high quality publications** (however, the manner in which the **quality** of the publication is measured has not been included), **ability to identify and acknowledge new ideas and novelty in own research and collaborative research**, ability to **accurately respond to the needs and demands of the stakeholders** as opposed to swaying to popular or current trends and beliefs in the field **is vital**, experience providing **feedback and performing peer review**.

One respondent also commented on the importance of **research experience**. Experience in the research field will **help guide and create the skills** needed to **recognize novel high-quality ideas**. Extensive **collaboration and contribution to the ideas of early career researchers could thus be harmful**.

Ability to write cohesive strategies and plans?

The respondents perceived that a researcher can practically demonstrate their ability to write cohesive strategies and plans through securing **research funding approvals**, recognition of **larger and wider objectives and strategies within the research plan**, research leading to **policy recommendations** (however, this criterion was recognized as research field specific and thus not relevant to all researchers), **manager duties and team lead roles** was also considered as an effective way for demonstrating strategy skills.

However, some respondents did not consider strategic writing and/or planning as being relevant researcher skills or criteria.

Biggest challenges for early career researchers

The respondents were asked to provide feedback on the most important or considerable challenges early career researchers experience, especially regarding researcher assessment. An overview of the respondents' feedback can be found below.

Early career researchers were considered being at a **disadvantage** when trying to compete for **funding applications, publication collaborations, establish networks with business industries and senior researchers**. The recognition of **researcher contribution and research takes time**, and thus they are at a considerable disadvantage when competing with more senior researchers for funding applications or securing investment from stakeholders, which **consequently further impacts their ability to develop their career and compete**. This issue may also encourage early career researchers to **merely publish as much in as least amount of time as possible, harming quality and innovation**.

In addition, early career researchers were viewed in **need of further support** from both their **supervisors**, their **research team**, their **peers in the research field**, and **the UAS in general**. The respondents suggested that UAS's are currently **not designed to support** the development of **publication**, meaning that **early career researchers continue to be 'behind'** and at a disadvantage compared to more senior researchers who already possess an impressive publication portfolio.

Further still, early career **researchers require guidance, knowledge and support in addition to just ideation or brainstorming**. Whilst examples were not provided by the respondents, **access to existing stakeholders and research networks** could prove very important. However, another respondent claimed that early career researchers are often dependent on other researchers' ideas, projects and networks. Nevertheless, this may be an issue which is difficult to resolve at a UAS as researchers need to collaborate with local stakeholders and thus not granted as much 'independence' as University researchers. It may therefore be an necessity for UAS researchers to accept that their early career development requires a level of collaboration and dependence on other researchers.

A lack of teamwork and support from researchers was identified as another need for early career researchers. If senior researchers feel the **need to protect their knowledge, experience, specialization and/or networks**, it ultimately makes **career development difficult for early career researchers**. Thus, the **values of teamwork, cooperation, comradeship and solidarity** need to be better **established**.

Finally, one respondent claimed that **Universities** currently hold the **privilege of selecting the 'best' researchers** which impact upon the effectiveness of research of the UAS and on the experience of the researchers at the UAS. This would suggest that **UAS's need to become**

more attractive to researchers and also provide **well developed career paths** (potentially tenure tracks) which help to both **enhance the skills of the researchers and support their career development**.

Researcher Supervisors & Researcher Evaluation Team

Research Department	Number
Principal Research Scientist Supervisors	
BIO	1/1
TECH	1/1
EDU	1/1
Total	3/3 (100%)
Researcher Evaluation Team	
BIO	1/1
TECH	2/2
EDU	1/1

Role of Research Impact

Research impact was considered an **important** aspect when evaluating researchers. 100% of the respondents either **completely agreed (57%)** or **somewhat agreed (43%)** with research impact being an essential component of the researcher assessment.

In the survey **research impact** was understood as the potential impact of the research itself. The quality of the research was therefore focused upon in this question.

Demonstrating and Measuring Research Impact

The respondents were asked to provide feedback on the suitability of the following criteria for measuring research impact:

- Multiple authors or research contributors,
- Use of a multidisciplinary approach (such as authors from different academic fields, inclusion of multiple academic fields in publications, presentation of research at multidisciplinary conferences etc.),
- Research conducted in collaboration with stakeholders,
- Research conducted in collaboration with diverse stakeholders,
- Demonstrated relevance of research to current local societal issues,
- Demonstrated relevance of research to current international societal issues,
- Demonstrated relevance of research in future (expected duration of research relevance),
- Demonstrated practical applicability of research in local society (applicable to local businesses, local non-profit organizations, local non-profit institutions, local policies etc.),

- Demonstrated practical applicability of research in international society (applicable to international businesses, international non-profit organizations, international government institutions etc.),
- Demonstrated practical applicability of research in UAS study units,
- Accessibility of research at all levels of society (such as academics, private business owners, policymakers, educators, ordinary citizens etc.),

Analysis of Research Impact Criteria:

The respondents were asked to comment on the list of criteria as appropriate measures for research impact.

The results of the respondents can be found below:

The following criteria were primarily **agreed upon** as the most relevant criteria for measuring research impact:

- **Demonstrated practical applicability of research in international society** (applicable to international businesses, international non-profit organizations, international government institutions etc.) (86% completely agreed, 14% somewhat agree).
- **Demonstrated relevance of research in future** (expected duration of research relevance), (71% completely agree, 29% somewhat agree).
- **Research conducted in collaboration with stakeholders** (71% completely agree, 29% somewhat agree).
- **Demonstrated relevance of research to current international societal issues**, (71% completely agree, 29% somewhat agree).

- **Research conducted in collaboration with diverse stakeholders**, (72% completely agree, 14% somewhat agree, 14% unsure).
- **Demonstrated practical applicability of research in local society** (applicable to local businesses, local non-profit organizations, local non-profit institutions, local policies etc.) (72% completely agree, 14% somewhat agree, 14% unsure).
- **Accessibility of research at all levels of society** (such as academics, private business owners, policymakers, educators, ordinary citizens etc.) (43% completely agree, 57% somewhat agree).
- **Multiple authors or research contributors** (43% completely agree, 57% somewhat agree).
- **Use of a multidisciplinary approach** (such as authors from different academic fields, inclusion of multiple academic fields in publications, presentation of research at multidisciplinary conferences etc.) (43% completely agree, 43% somewhat agree, 14% unsure).
- **Demonstrated relevance of research to current local societal issues** (29% completely agree, 71% somewhat agree).

For the following criteria, whilst the majority of respondents did agree that these were relevant measures for research impact, these criteria were also most ***disagreed upon***:

- **Demonstrated practical applicability of research in UAS study units** (14% completely agree, 57% somewhat agree, 14% unsure, 15% somewhat disagree).

Whilst the respondents generally agreed upon the potential criteria for measuring research impact, the multidisciplinary research, collaboration with multiple authors and/or diverse stakeholders, and the applicability of research with the study units of the education institution were the most disputed. However, these criteria were also not completely dismissed or considered as irrelevant.

In addition, whilst research impact was recognized as an important consideration in researcher evaluation, the following points were highlighted:

- HAMK has mission orientated research so research impact is vital.
- Research impact and target groups for this research impact are important to be defined.
- Impact can be defined and understood in multiple ways 'scientific impact, practical impact, educational impact.' The type of impact being measured or obtained is also very important.
- The type of impact or the extent of the impact needs to be considered to the researcher and their respective career. The assessment of the impact thus needs to take in to account if the researcher is early-, mid-, or senior career level.

Role of Researcher influence

The role of researcher influence in the researcher evaluation was considered as important by 100% of the respondents. 29% completely agreed and 71% somewhat agreed that the influence of the researcher should be included in the researcher assessment.

The respondents were asked to provide feedback on the suitability of the following criteria for measuring researcher influence:

- Role in funding applications,
- Role in published publications or other products or formats of research (such as patents, technology, software, etc.),
- Collaboration with different academic fields in projects or research related activities,
- Collaboration with different stakeholders in projects or research related activities (such as businesses, policymakers, non-profit organizations etc.),
- Collaboration with a diverse range of people from different backgrounds,
- Collaboration with UAS study units,
- Participation in local research conferences, lectures, webinars, presentations, panels etc.,
- Participation in international conferences, lectures, webinars, presentations, panels etc.,
- Participation in research mobility programs,
- Role in teaching activities,
- Feedback on teaching activities from students and/or colleagues,
- Role in researcher supervision activities,
- Feedback on supervision activities from students and/or colleagues,
- Range of different methodological skills utilized in projects, research activities, teaching activities and supervision activities,
- Use of different formats of communication (such as articles, presentations, speeches, workshops etc.),
- Experience in communicating with different audiences (such as academic audiences, policymakers, private businesses, ordinary citizens etc.)

Analysis of Researcher Influence Criteria:

The respondents were asked to comment on the list of criteria as appropriate measures for researcher influence.

The results of the respondents can be found below:

The following criteria were primarily **agreed upon** as the most relevant criteria for measuring research impact:

- **Use of different formats of communication** (such as articles, presentations, speeches, workshops etc.) (86% completely agree, 14% somewhat agree).
- **Collaboration with different stakeholders in projects or research related activities** (such as businesses, policymakers, non-profit organizations etc.) (86% completely agree, 14% somewhat agree).
- **Role in funding applications**, (86% completely agree, 14% somewhat agree).
- **Experience in communicating with different audiences** (such as academic audiences, policymakers, private businesses, ordinary citizens etc.) (71% completely agree, 29% somewhat agree).
- **Range of different methodological skills utilized in projects, research activities, teaching activities and supervision activities**, (71% completely agree, 29% somewhat agree).
- **Participation in international conferences, lectures, webinars, presentations, panels etc.**, (71% completely agree, 29% somewhat agree).
- **Collaboration with a diverse range of people from different backgrounds** (71% completely agree, 29% somewhat agree).

For the following criteria, whilst the majority of respondents did agree that these were relevant measures of researcher influence, these criteria were also most **disagreed upon**:

- **Role in researcher supervision activities** (57% completely agree, 29% somewhat agree, 14% unsure).

- **Feedback on supervision activities from students and/or colleagues**, (43% completely agree, 43% somewhat agree, 14% unsure).
- **Participation in research mobility programs** (29% completely agree, 57% somewhat agree, 14% unsure).
- **Role in teaching activities** (29% completely agree, 43% somewhat agree, 28% unsure).
- **Collaboration with UAS study units**, (14% completely agree, 72% somewhat agree, 14% unsure).
- **Feedback on teaching activities from students and/or colleagues**, (71% somewhat agree, 29% unsure).
- **Role in published publications or other products or formats of research** (such as patents, technology, software, etc.) (86% completely agree, 14% somewhat disagree).

In addition, whilst researcher influence was recognized as an important consideration in researcher evaluation, the following points were highlighted:

- The type of activities and to what extent are these activities performed by the researcher, need to be considered in the assessment.
- The researcher's self-assessment is also a vital component in understanding researcher influence.

Role of Cooperation and Collaboration

The respondents were asked to what extent the following criteria were relevant to measuring cooperation and collaboration skills:

- Participation in either funding applications or research, which has multidisciplinary involvement.
- Participation in either funding applications or research, which considers multistakeholder involvement.
- Researcher involvement with other academic institutions.
- Researcher involvement with private sector institutions.
- Researcher involvement in UAS study units.
- Researcher involvement with other societal institutions.

Analysis of Collaboration and Cooperation criteria

The results of the respondents can be found below:

The following criteria were primarily **agreed upon** as the most relevant criteria for measuring collaboration and cooperation for UAS researchers:

- **Participation in either funding applications or research, which considers multistakeholder involvement** (86% completely agreed, 14% somewhat agreed).
- **Participation in either funding applications or research, which has multidisciplinary involvement** (71% completely agreed, 29% somewhat agreed).
- **Researcher involvement with other academic institutions** (43% completely agreed, 57% somewhat agreed).
- **Researcher involvement with private sector institutions** (43% completely agreed, 57% somewhat agreed).
- **Researcher involvement in UAS study units** (100% somewhat agreed).

For the following criteria, whilst the majority of respondents did agree that these were relevant measures of researcher influence, these criteria were also most disagreed upon:

- **Researcher involvement with other societal institutions** (29% completely agree, 57% somewhat agree, 14% unsure).

Opinions and Comments on: Communication Skills, Marketing Skills, Cooperation Skills, Flexibility, and Strategic Planning

The respondents were also asked to comment and provide feedback on how, in their opinion, researchers could demonstrate skills in **effective communication**, their ability to **market ideas, research and projects**, their ability to **learn and cooperate**, their ability to **be flexible with ideas and respond to new research and findings**, ability to **write cohesive strategies**

and plans. Below is an overview of the feedback provided by the respondents:

Comparing Results: Important Consideration

The next section will discuss the main themes and tensions identified from the survey results of both the Principal Research Scientists and Researcher Supervisors and Evaluation Team. The most important considerations from the results are also presented.

Assessment Themes

Theme	Principal Research Scientists	Supervisors & Evaluators	Considerations
Adapting research to real world settings	<p>"Demonstrated work-place learning."</p> <p>"The impact is the proven change it has in the real world: How it has produced practical innovations/ new solutions like curricula, services, products, new offerings and business."</p> <p>"It should be comprehensive, fair and adaptable, considering both academic metrics and contributions to science and society."</p>	<p>'Strong scientific background combined with practical view and open attitude towards collaboration.'</p> <p>"They should have a clear vision of the challenges and an idea how to tackle it in a way that can be adapted in a reasonably short time."</p>	<p>Scientific backgrounds and research skills need to be combined and adapted to real world settings, challenges and needs.</p> <p>Working with stakeholders requires researchers to operate in the business world and real social contexts.</p> <p>Researchers also recognized the need to be able to conduct research which is applicable to real world settings and has an impact on the real world.</p> <p>The need for 'real workplace learning' was seen as important and the need for their research to have an influence in the real world and not only among academics or scientists.</p>
Diverse communication skills, channels and platforms	<p>"No research is complete, before it is communicated and people are aware of its existence."</p> <p>"Balanced ability to oral and written communication a) within your own organisation, b) to neighbouring organisations and c) to the</p>	<p>"Addition to scientific journal also professional and blog publications are important. Presenting results or ideas for business audience is effective."</p> <p>"by speaking the same language with business and</p>	<p>Communication skills are extremely important for UAS researchers.</p> <p>Communications skills include the ability to effectively communicate with different audiences, through different channels and also utilize</p>

	general public. Note: communication as a two-way activity."	public sector representatives."	different communication platforms effectively.
Promoting novel visions and risk-taking	<p>" Let's appreciate diversity and the ability to try, even with a little risk."</p> <p>" Provides understanding of the value: ecological, social and economic value of the research beyond value to the researchers' career."</p> <p>" Impact of research: also important on going research and those research applications which didn't get funding."</p>	<p>" Ability to identify research gaps based on previous research; ability to create innovative research designs."</p> <p>" There is no criteria capturing the research vision."</p> <p>Important skills: "curiosity."</p>	<p>The actual ability of researchers to come up with innovative and visionary ideas is very important and needs to be acknowledged.</p> <p>The consideration of unsuccessful project applications or funding applications also helps promote risk taking and being inventive beyond 'guaranteed' acceptance.</p> <p>Recognizing risk taking and unsuccess helps to promote innovative ideas from researchers and enhance the quality of research.</p>
Importance of self-reflection	<p>"a researcher should be able to describe their competences in practice during their work tasks. Not only research papers."</p> <p>"Strategic thinking in terms of his/hers own focus area & research group in it: objectives & metrics for short & long period and how to develop the focus are / research team in the future - meaning the vision how he/she thinks the field will develop/change."</p>	<p>"External evaluation by research scholars is important but also forms of peer and self-assessment becomes important."</p> <p>"Challenges for ECR: Challenges in identifying and describing own skills and competencies; challenges in reflecting own strengths and weaknesses as a researcher....Difficulties in setting goals for own research."</p>	<p>Self assessment needs to capture how the researcher evaluates their own strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>The strength and weaknesses and possible direction of own work.</p> <p>How they compensate the weaknesses or utilize their strengths should also be considered as this demonstrates flexibility, and a visionary and strategic mindset.</p> <p>It also captures their ability to think and apply their research and themselves in real world settings.</p> <p>How to use peer review assessment is also vital.</p>

			The researchers experience in peer reviewing is also important as it showcases their ability to be responsive and flexible to different ideas etc.
Non-related research experience is also important	<p>“Learning: you can check the cv from the perspective of lifelong learning -is the researcher trying to constantly acquire new skills or is she/he just looking at things through one basic education? Has the researcher changed professional fields and worked in multidisciplinary teams? What kind of concrete work has the researcher done with diverse stakeholders?”</p>		<p>A CV which also considers the importance of other educational or work-related experiences is important. How these can be applied to their work as researchers.</p> <p>UAS researchers are expected to work with real stakeholders in the real world, their own real-world experiences provides them with skills, understanding and means to do so effectively.</p>
Impact differs across fields	<p>’it will take years or tens of years to see the actual impacts. Therefore, short-term results such as list of publications are important for career progress.’</p> <p>“ Recognition of quality research before numeric indicators can show it (eg. citations take time to come).”</p> <p>“ impact of research difficult to measure and should not be considered in the researcher assessment.”</p>		<p>It is important to consider and identify the different factors which influence the type of impact which can be achieved in different fields.</p> <p>Criteria should take this into consideration, and it is important to get insight from those fields.</p> <p>This is also vital in promoting or enhancing the impact done in those fields by removing barriers and supporting researchers from different fields in different ways.</p>

Adapting research to real world settings

UAS researchers are expected to work closely with real stakeholders and thus need to be able to understand and accurately respond to their needs and challenges. Thus **requires UAS researchers to understand the real-life context stakeholders operate in and speak the same ‘industry language’ as their stakeholders.**

Strategic thinking is also extremely important as UAS researchers may need to **resolve immediate issues in a short period of time**. **Experience working with stakeholders** is thus a considerable advantage for UAS researchers to have and will aid them in understanding how their **research can be applied to the real world** outside of academic and research circles.

Diverse communication skills, channels and platforms

The ability to **communicate or present results or ideas effectively to businesses and different audiences** was highlighted as an essential skill. This includes understanding how to **utilize different communication channels and platforms** for different purposes and presenting research and research outputs on different formats. Research dissemination was also identified as being important, and this included attempting to **share research as openly as possible**.

Promoting novel visions and risk-taking

It was identified that the research ideas themselves, their diversity, and the **extent of innovation and novelty applied by the researcher** should be recognized in the assessment. A researcher's visionary and **strategic mindset** was considered by some as being even **more important than researcher experience** itself. The researcher's ability to recognize how their research impacts and/or extends to wider objectives and strategies, outside of their own discipline, is also crucial. The assessment needs to be able to capture the researcher's curiosity and their ability to think innovatively.

Researchers also acknowledged that research needs to have a **more profound objective than merely enhance the research career** of the researcher themselves. Importance was given to the researcher's ability to **generate fresh ideas**, and it was highlighted that both **successful and unsuccessful project applications and funding applications could be used to demonstrate this**. In this sense, risk-taking and diversity should be promoted, recognized and rewarded in the researcher assessment.

Importance of self-reflection

Self-assessment and peer assessment are viewed as being crucial in the assessment process. The ability for researchers to be able to **strategically analyze and reflect on their research is vital**. Self-assessment highlights the motivations and expectations of researchers and ensures they match that of the institution.

If self-assessment is to become integrated into the researcher evaluation process, **early career researchers need to be guided on documenting their achievements** and activities from the start of their career. In addition, early career researchers need to become more aware of their strengths and weaknesses and use these to guide their career development.

Peer review and feedback from stakeholders was also highlighted as important. **Researchers need to gain experience in providing feedback to their peers** and utilizing feedback from others to guide their career development.

Non-related research experience is also important

Other activities, for example involvement in quality peer review and peer support, were also identified as important criteria. **Practical work experience outside of the research field**, and the different roles and duties undertaken by the researcher are all important.

In addition, the **motivation for life-long learning** within a researcher was considered important alongside their **activeness in the field** and practical **demonstration of cooperation** between others.

Impact differs across fields

The discipline itself and and/or research field were also recognized as important considerations. **Different academic and research fields require different ways of measuring, identifying and understanding impact.** In some fields or types of research, **impact can be experienced relatively quickly**, whilst in **other research this may take more time.** This is also true for publications. In some fields publishing research results can be completed relatively quickly, whilst in others, publishing is slower and more limited. This should not however undermine the value of the research itself. Diversity in research is needed and should be recognized. **Both long-term and short-term impact and results are needed**, and they will appear differently in different fields and disciplines.

Researcher Career Path Themes

Theme	Principal Research Scientists	Supervisors & Evaluators	Considerations
Support for networking	<p>"Whenever you enter new culture you cannot know what are the criteria and standards. It takes time to learn all that in new culture."</p> <p>"Yhteistyökuvioiden rakentaminen paikallisten yritysten kanssa... Tähän ei sovi pitkät jaarittelevat palaverit eikä tapahtumat, joista ei ole konkreettista hyötyä yrityksille."</p>		<p>Need to consider how the career development and tenure track can support the networking of researchers with other researcher, academic fields etc.</p> <p>UAS also needs to consider how it can best create situations and navigate the ability for researchers to make connections at businesses and get potential 'key partners' where at least ECR can start off their research career.</p>
	"It is very difficult to make the next step from PhD to		Need to consider how ECR can direct and be

Support between peers	<p>post doc, and to be accepted to a research group as a junior researcher because you might not have an impressive list of publications yet.”</p> <p>“It is the collaboration which is difficult for young researchers to find and establish the research collaboration with industry and senior researchers.”</p> <p>“Lack of colleagues support. Lack of researcher team and its support.”</p>		<p>more in charge of their own research.</p> <p>How to ensure that ECR have the opportunity to try to gain more publications and recognition before trying to network with more senior researchers.</p> <p>Potential research groups with ECR's.</p>
Importance of stable and durable research	<p>“Activities for making research available, accessible and understandable for general public take time, but can greatly advance the spread of scientific knowledge.”</p> <p>Cohesive plans and strategy skills: “ Pitkään jatkuneet yritysyhteistyökuviot.”</p>		<p>Stable and long partnerships or collaborations with a few stakeholders may be more important in regards to research or project impact in comparison to having a lot of short lived collaborations.</p> <p>The stability and long term thinking needed for projects or research to succeed needs to be recognized.</p>

Support for networking

The principal research scientists highlighted that cooperation and **collaboration with local stakeholders is often difficult**. This is especially the case for researchers who are either not from the local area, or not from Finland in general. A **lack of local knowledge, existing networks and language barriers** thus, makes networking with stakeholders challenging. All researchers, in particular coming from outside of the local region and/or country, should be better supported in engaging with local stakeholders.

In addition, **networking with other researchers** was also recognized as being **challenging**, especially for **early career researchers** who do not yet have an impressive track record. Early career researchers and mostly in need of networks yet are at considerable disadvantage in securing them. **Support and active inclusion** from fellow researchers are thus important.

It was suggested that **UAS** should actively **set up networking events** which are beneficial for stakeholders and allow all researchers (early, mid and senior level), **to engage with local stakeholders and build networks.**

It is important to consider how career development can be supported at HAMK. How can researchers, especially in the early career stages and those researchers who are not from the area, be supported. Some proposals could potentially be mentor programs where senior researchers can help introduce early career and/or international researchers to existing networks, and/or roundtable discussions between research departments and academic staff, where cooperation and collaboration are actively explored.

Universities of Applied Sciences need to develop a concrete strategy for recruiting **local key stakeholders and/or partners**, which could play a central role in helping early career researchers and international researchers make their first networks. In addition, it was highlighted that Universities of Applied Sciences need to focus **arranging stakeholder networking** events which actively focus on **finding cooperation opportunities** between researchers and stakeholders. This requires arranging networking events which are **directly beneficial to the stakeholders who are invited.**

Support between peers

Early career researchers are **dependent** on the **research plans and projects** of other more **advanced researchers.** However, many early career researchers continue to be at a disadvantage as they require more publications, networks and or successful funding application to be included in research projects. It was suggested that senior researchers should try to include early career researchers whenever possible. Senior researchers should have a form of responsibility in building up the career of early career researchers, to ensure they gradually become more appealing to external research groups and stakeholders.

Here, there is great emphasis on the need to **support** the **success of the overall research team** as opposed to the success of the individual researchers. Thus, researcher peers should support each other in presenting opportunities and supporting each other's research careers.

Importance of stable and durable research

Some researchers noted that for some research fields, the impact of research and projects may take a long time. **Stable and long-term cooperation and collaboration** with stakeholders are **best for yielding actual impact** and results. Long-term collaboration with stakeholders is significant and enhances the quality and extended impact of research. Again, the recruitment of **key local stakeholders** may help to establish durable, stable and quality partnerships and thus yield quality research impact.

Main Tensions

Theme	Principal Research Scientists	Supervisors & Evaluators	Considerations
Multidisciplinary vs Specialization	<p>"if you work with other research institutions and universities but with people with the same disciplinary background or perhaps even your old colleagues it does not necessarily indicate increased influence and impact"</p> <p>"Collaborations, diverse, range, extent of cooperation (numerics can support this)."</p> <p>"Publications with some variation in topics and collaborators, up to date questions in published papers."</p> <p>"In a different scientific fields there are various practices how the researcher can act and proceed. This might cause challenges."</p> <p>"I think it is not a challenge if researchers are working in their own field or discipline based on educations and experiences. Multidisciplinary research is brilliant idea but has been mis-implemented here."</p>	<p>Biggest Skills: "understanding the need of cooperation with other disciplines."</p> <p>"open attitude towards collaboration."</p> <p>Cohesive Strategy Skills: "Have a vision from your own field and link it with other disciplines."</p> <p>Research flexibility: "It is also important to cooperate internally with different discipline."</p>	<p>Different fields will need different considerations for the qualitative criteria. Whilst criteria is the same, we may need to consider what aspects of the criteria are most valued. e.g. In some fields publications take longer due to experiments needing longer time to be seen credible, some fields require long extensive partnerships with businesses whilst others can achieve more in shorter time period but with more stakeholders.</p> <p>Need to make sure that multidisciplinary is promoted in a manner which benefits the research and its impact.</p> <p>Need to make sure multidisciplinary is approached in a manner where researchers benefit from the multidisciplinary interaction and not just done for the sake of 'multidisciplinary.'</p> <p>Researchers need to be aware of the novel potential of multidisciplinary and the skills it enhances.</p>
	<p>"Open mind attitude for new ideas. Skills to find new ideas based on own and collaborators expertise."</p> <p>"The impact is the proven change it has in the real world: How it has produced practical innovations/ new</p>	<p>"Addition to scientific journal also professional and blog publications are important. Presenting results or ideas for business audience is effective."</p> <p>Biggest skills:</p>	<p>The vision and strategy of HAMK needs to explicitly recognize the importance of business cooperation and collaboration. This needs to be communicated effectively to researchers.</p>

<p>Importance of Business Industry Cooperation & Entrepreneurship Skills</p>	<p>solutions like curricula, services, products, new offerings and business."</p> <p>"Ability to market ideas is not necessary."</p> <p>"We should not require the researchers to become entrepreneurs."</p> <p>"We don not market ideas. If we have business ideas, then it is better to establish a separate company with its own cash flow. UAS is educational institute, and research activities will enhance our knowledge creation for it and produce both short-term and long-term positive impacts to regional business."</p>	<p>"To transfer researchers' skills to solve complex challenges companies or other stakeholders have!"</p> <p>Biggest skills: "Ability to operate in the business world and social contexts."</p>	<p>Researchers need to be aware of the importance of business relations and partnerships from the standpoint of the UAS and understand how their role is to enhance this through their research activities.</p> <p>How entrepreneurial skills intertwine with research and research skills need to be explicitly explained.</p> <p>There is great misunderstanding here.</p>
<p>The Centrality of Publications in Researcher Assessment</p>	<p>"Recognition of quality research before numeric indicators can show it (e.g. citations take time to come)."</p> <p>"it will take years or tens of years to see the actual impacts. Therefore, short-term results such as list of publications are important for career progress"</p> <p>"priority should be peer reviewed publications, should be the focus of researcher impact."</p> <p>"Most important criteria: " Publications. Quality of publications."</p>	<p>"Mere focus on number of publications and amount of funding received."</p> <p>"Journal article based metrics (number of articles in scientific journals, personal citation index, impact factors of journals etc.). 2. Volume of the project funding. 3. Research leading or supervising actions." - ineffective criteria for ECR."</p>	<p>Researchers may still be very used to and familiar with the role of publications in their assessment and in funding call etc. They need to become aware of the other criteria which can be used.</p> <p>Researchers do still recognize the need to identify quality publications over the mere quantity.</p> <p>Publications will still play an important role in many researchers career, however the centrality or the manner in which they should be assessed needs to be recaptured.</p>

Multidisciplinary vs Specialization

Researcher evaluators and supervisors highlighted the **importance of a multi-, inter-, transdisciplinary** approach in researcher impact.

Some researchers also recognized the importance of multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary approaches in research, but **other researchers felt that specialization** in their field created **significant impact** and ‘random’ ideas from colleagues will disrupt research progress. Thus, in their opinion, **multidisciplinary may even hinder the ability to show impact** in an established field. Different research fields may need to approach inter-, trans-, and multidisciplinary requirements differently, however, as the research strategy at HAMK promotes inter-, trans-, and multidisciplinary approaches, these should be recognized and considered important by the researchers.

Whilst collaboration between different researchers and research departments is promoted and expected at HAMK, these collaborations need to be justified and rationalized.

Collaboration needs to ensure that they benefit the research, the researchers and/or the stakeholders.

Business & Entrepreneurship Skills

The researcher supervisors and evaluators recognized **businesses and entrepreneurship skills as being vital** for researchers, and the **importance of business industry stakeholders**. They identified businesses as being target stakeholders for UAS researchers. Entrepreneurship skills are vital in **helping researchers understand how to cooperate with businesses** and also **understand their needs and challenges**.

Whilst **some researchers** also **acknowledged the importance of business collaboration** and the need for research to respond to their expertise and needs, **other researchers** felt there was **too much focus on business cooperation and collaboration** at HAMK. Others did **not recognize the applicability or appropriateness of entrepreneurial skills** with researchers at UAS's. There is thus a **misunderstanding or differing of opinions** on the **centrality of business industry stakeholders** and the need for UAS researchers to possess **entrepreneurial skills**.

The vision and strategy of HAMK needs to explicitly recognize the importance of business cooperation and collaboration. This also needs to be **communicated effectively** to researchers. In particular, how **entrepreneurial skills intertwine with research and research skills** need to be explicitly explained. There is a miscommunication and/or misunderstanding in what entrepreneurial skills are or how they are applied to UAS researchers.

Researchers need to understand the importance of business relations and partnerships from the standpoint of the UAS and understand their role and duty as UAS researchers to solve local and regional issues of local stakeholders.

The Centrality of Publications in Researcher Assessment

Researcher evaluators and supervisors acknowledged that **publications, citations or the impact factor** of journals are **not effective** in capturing skills of researchers.

Some **researchers (few)** also **acknowledge this** and feel that quality over quantity needs to be promoted. However, **the majority** of surveyed **researchers** continued to **promote the centrality of publications** and felt this is the best way to assess researchers. Publications are the best way to showcase impact as other forms of impact may take a long time to be identified.

Some research fields can actively and relatively quickly publish new data and research results, whilst in other fields this takes more time. Thus, the mere number of publications does not suffice in assessing researcher competence. However, the **researchers remained very reliant on the role of publications** in the researcher's assessment process, and they thus **need to be exposed to alternative assessment criteria**.

Whilst publications remain an important sub-category of the researcher assessment process, its centrality needs to be recaptured. There needs to be a balance in which UAS researchers can engage in publishing, but it does not become central to their role.

Interviews

Overview

The aim of the interviews was to gather further understanding of how researchers and researcher supervisors and evaluators interpret researcher evaluation processes. The aim of the interviews was to better understand what the respondents viewed as the most important skills and competencies of UAS researchers and what type of criteria they felt were appropriate in measuring these.

Participants were invited to the interview, and they were able to schedule the interview date and time themselves. The interviews were conducted over team and were recorded and transcribed. The interviews were semi-structured and whilst certain questions guided the direction of the interview, the participants were given the opportunity and freedom to speak as they wish. The participant was able to conduct the interview in either English or Finnish.

Two main themes were explored: **Research Evaluation**, and **Researcher Evaluation**. The same interview was conducted on both the principal research scientists and researcher supervisors and evaluators. The questions were slightly modified depending on the participant to gather both the perspectives of the researchers when being assessed and the researcher supervisors and evaluators when assessing researchers. The interview guide can be found in **Appendix 3**.

Participants

Research Department	Number
Principal Research Scientists	
BIO	anonymous
TECH	anonymous
EDU	anonymous
SOCHEALTH	anonymous
Total	11/37 (29%)
Principal Research Scientist Supervisors	
BIO	anonymous
TECH	anonymous
EDU	anonymous
Total	1/3 (33%)
Researcher Evaluation Team	
BIO	anonymous
TECH	anonymous
EDU	anonymous
Total	0/4 (0%)

Findings

Thematic analysis was used to categorize the findings. Four different themes were identified **research, development, innovation, and other competencies. Other important considerations** outside of these four categories were also acknowledged.

Research

Practical application and benefit:

Research conducted by UAS researchers needed to demonstrate practical applicability to and benefit. Research should have the aim and objective at solving problems in real-world

contexts and thus be beneficial outside of the academic world. For UAS researchers this ability to operate in the real-life world, use research skills and knowledge to resolve stakeholder issues and provide concrete solutions was considered pivotal.

Value added

One important factor of research conducted in UAS's was 'value added.' This means that all research being conducted should be adding some form of value. It was also considered important for this value to be practically 'valuable' especially for stakeholders. However, this 'value added' did not always need to be in the form of a physical product or service. New methods, tools and or the inclusion of new multi-, inter-, or transdisciplinary approaches could all be viewed as 'adding value.'

High stakeholder involvement and benefit

In regard to research, the participants identified that the extensive inclusion of stakeholders in the research was important. For development projects to be valuable and beneficial to stakeholders, it was considered vital to extensively include stakeholders in the actual project itself. Participants highlighted that close collaboration with stakeholders during applied research helps to ensure that the needs, challenges and unique context of the stakeholders in considered. This consideration increases the likelihood of research outputs and results to be valuable to stakeholders.

Regional, national and international strategy

Participants highlighted the importance of considering regional, national and international contexts in regard to research. UAS research was important for regional development, and thus, the regional context needs to be focused upon, and regional stakeholders engaged with. Nevertheless, social impact is also paramount and considering national and international strategies within region and how the regional research can benefit from these and in turn contribute towards these is crucial.

Peer recognition

The interviews highlighted the importance peer recognition plays in validating the quality of research, the competence of researchers and enhances trust within stakeholders. Peer reviewed publications were highlighted by some researchers as being central, as this means the work of researchers has been acknowledged and reinforced by others in their field. However, peer feedback and testimonials were also viewed as vital outside of publications. Receiving feedback from peers within the same field is important for highlighting research impact and reinforcing the skills and experience of researchers.

Diverse collaboration

International collaboration and cooperation between researchers were recognized as being important as it promotes the recognition of diverse perspectives and innovation. As one researcher cannot be expected to be an expert in all aspects, cooperation between different

specialists and fields was also viewed as being important for bringing about new ideas and solutions. However, the interviews also highlighted that international collaboration, and collaboration in general, needs to be carefully planned and justified. Collaboration for the sake of collaboration should not be promoted.

Effective research planning and management

The interviews highlighted that research planning and management are vital skills for researchers. Thus, it is important to assess how effectively researchers have been able to plan, manage and execute their research.

Effective data collection

Collecting actual data from the field was also recognized as being vital in research, especially in applied sciences. Researchers should thus be skilled in collecting data and be physically present in the field in which the data is being collected from. Data collection methodologies should be well planned, justified and ethically prepared for.

Variation of researcher role

The variation of roles in which researchers are experienced was also considered important. This was especially seen as the case for senior researchers. Senior researchers should have a responsibility in making room for younger or early career researchers. AS an example, the interviewees highlighted that having researchers who are also first authors indicates bad collaboration skills. Thus, the career stage of the researchers should be acknowledged as this impacts upon the variation of researcher role which is expected of them.

Development

Practical local benefit

The interviews highlighted that the local benefit created, especially for local stakeholders, in UAS research is the most important. However, whilst local development is important, it is also vital to ensure research can be applied at the national and international level. Development at UAS means implementing research into everyday life. However, how impact should be measured differs between respondents. For some, the use of hard numbers was viewed as the most concrete way of measuring impact. However, understandably achieving this may differ between different research fields.

Transfer of knowledge to real world

The interviews highlighted that UAS researchers have a great responsibility in ensuring knowledge which has been gained through their research is adequately transferred into everyday life. This means that it needs to be communicated in language which is understandable to the stakeholders, various communication platforms should be utilized to reach different audiences, research should be presented at open events and interaction with ordinary citizens pursued, face-to-face contact with stakeholders should be promoted and

researchers should attempt to utilize and adapt research results to suit the needs of different types of stakeholders.

Education and research integration

Integrating research into education, especially into the UAS study programs, was also considered vital as it ensures that the next workforce generation can actively benefit from it. This integration can be pursued in many ways, whilst some UAS Principal Research Scientists will lecturer and actively teach, present and discuss their research in the classroom, using students when conducting the research itself and using the research as classroom tasks (for example brainstorming solutions) all contribute. Integrating research into education was also viewed as a manner of transferring research into everyday life. However, one interviewee expressed that integrating research into education should be optional and not enforced. Whilst this view is understandable the research strategy of many UAS's such as HAMK, is to ensure that research benefits the educational mission of the UAS.

Importance of international partners

International recognition of research was considered important in the interviews. The interviewees suggested that by incorporating international strategies into research and collaborating with international partners, stakeholders and other researchers this could be achieved. Ensuring researchers are active in international networks is thus important. Similarly, the UAS should attempt to promote internationalization through international UAS partnerships, organizing or attending events, participating in researcher exchange programs etc.

UAS researchers require agility

The interviews highlighted that a key skill for UAS researchers is their ability to be agile, flexible and capable of adapting to different research needs. This means researchers need to have a good understanding of basic theories and researchers and be able to apply this to real life contexts. This agility also allows them to be more innovative and potentially take more risks. The ability of researchers to be able to adapt to their communication styles and the type of language they are using was also considered important. Being able to speak the same 'language' as stakeholders is vital for fully understanding their needs and issues.

Importance of collaboration

Collaboration with different researchers, partners and stakeholders was considered vital in applied research and development. Including stakeholders in applied research was considered especially important. Stakeholders are seen as the experts of their own unique situation and thus, their feedback and contribution are vital for developing solutions with practical value. In-depth inclusion and deep collaboration with stakeholders are therefore vital. Collaboration with other partners and researchers needs to be approached with caution. Selecting the correct collaborative partners is important and should be carefully considered.

Development also includes failure

The recognition of failure in applied research was also significant. Unsuccessful attempts at applied research or in providing solutions need to be considered as an important part of development. Failure helps to define what does ‘not work’ and why. This is also important as otherwise researchers will be afraid to take risks, innovate or try something new.

Nevertheless, ensuring that proper risk analysis has been conducted and the methods applied have been chosen rationally is also vital. Learning from this failure and fully understanding how it should impact upon future research is also necessary.

Impact and multi-, inter-, transdisciplinary approaches

Applying multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary approaches or collaborating with different research fields helps to increase the impact, applicability and innovative appeal for applied research. Whilst multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary needs to be applied differently in different research projects and different research fields and contexts, its importance and benefit should be recognized by researchers and utilized whenever possible.

Innovation

Importance of face-to-face networking

Face-to-face contact, especially with stakeholders, was considered vital for innovation. Face-to-face interaction helps to build trust and stable partnerships with stakeholders and allows for discussions and ideas to flow with more ease. In-depth discussions which are based on trust allow for a deeper understanding of stakeholder needs and issues and help to build better rapport.

Successful and unsuccessful ideas support innovation

For many of those interviews, value was recognized in both successful and unsuccessful research ideas and funding applications. AS UAS researchers rely on receiving funding to help actualize their research ideas, it is important for UAS researchers to be able to create high quality funding applications. Nevertheless, innovative ideas, which have not been successful in securing funding, should not be dismissed. It is vital for researchers to also be assessed on the quality of their funding applications even if these have not been successful, and securing funding is dependent upon many external factors. Success does not accurately depict talent, potential and innovation. Researchers can be encouraged to be daring and innovative if the quality of all of their funding applications (successful and unsuccessful) are considered. Activeness in applying is important as the skills required continue to be developed.

Innovation can be demonstrated in multiple ways

Innovation was viewed as a complicated and ambiguous term. The interviewees felt that it was important for all UAS's, in this case HAMK, to clearly define what they consider to be innovative and how this should be approached by researchers. It may include innovative

ideas, but also new collaborations, different methods etc. Innovation for applied research was considered as something which can be applied in the real world and is of practical use and benefit. In addition, innovation can be assessed in different ways. Activeness in pursuing innovative research ideas, consistency and persistence are important qualities as is the ability to be flexible and creative. Innovation cannot be measured through funding applications alone, as these do not always support the most innovative ideas but are highly dependent on the research field, the research theme and the funder. Thus, it is the presence of innovative skills which is important.

Career stage impacts innovation

Early career researchers were considered vital in securing innovation. Early career researchers are often highly motivated and although they have not been able to accomplish as much yet, their drive, persistence, activeness and consistency are important additions to research teams. Again, innovative skills, ideas and innovative potential are important to consider.

Practical experience can increase innovation

Practical experience, outside of research experience itself, is also important to consider. Practical experience allows for a different type of understanding and thus different types of ideas develop from these different experiences.

Education collaboration supports innovation

The diffusion of education with research was also seen as important for innovation. Ideas can flow between researchers and lecturers more easily if they have more opportunities to interact with each other. In addition, students are also important as their unique ideas and experiences help to drive new ideas and new approaches.

UAS organizational culture does not support innovation

It was also highlighted by the interviewees that innovation at UAS, where the research is dependent on actual companies, is limited. As it is the responsibility of UAS's to produce practical benefits to stakeholders, who often also invest money into these projects, the ability to take risks is more limited. This means that continued collaboration and networking is even more vital for UAS researchers as their innovative ideas need to be carefully justified.

Inclusion can lead to new insights

Research teams require different researchers with different experiences and different types of careers. Long careers do not always secure innovative thinking, flexibility and/or creativity. Different researchers are able to support the brainstorming of different ideas, providing crucial feedback and rotating ideas amongst different circles. In this sense, limiting ideas to only academic circles do not suffice. Applied research requires the inclusion of different types of stakeholders and co-creation with different research fields. Interaction opportunities need to be prioritized by researchers but opportunities for these should also be created by the UAS.

Practical benefits should be prioritized over novelty

For one interviewee, the acknowledgment that at UAS's the practical benefit and solution provided by research should outweigh its 'innovative' or 'new added' aspect. As UAS's are primarily responsible for creating practical solutions for regional stakeholders this should remain the main purpose. Innovation is important but researchers should not prioritize this over addressing the real needs of the stakeholders.

Other Competencies

Ability to combine theory with the real world

It was highlighted that UAS researchers need to have a good understanding of general theories, however, they need to be able to combine theories and modify these to be applicable in the real world. Transferring knowledge is also an important part of ensuring that applied research becomes ingrained into everyday life.

Variation of communication skills

Communication skills were identified as highly important. UAS researchers need to have a range of communication skills to allow them to communicate effectively with various audiences. Researchers need to communicate in the language most familiar with the stakeholders and be willing and competent in interacting in face-to-face situations. They also have to understand the best way to present research depending on the audience and/or situation. For example, presenting the research to students may be very different compared to presenting at an academic conference. This requires an understanding of what materials and mediums to use to ensure research is understandable and also which communication platforms and/or publication platforms to use to attract the correct audience.

Able to identify appropriate audiences

In connection with the theme above, researchers also need to be able to identify which audiences they need to attract and thereafter modify their communication and dissemination techniques. This may mean identifying how to best engage with the most appropriate target groups but also identify potential other audiences who would be interested or would benefit from the research.

Self-reflection skills

This skill is important for researchers to recognize. Each researcher needs to understand their own role in different projects and research teams and the value which they add. In addition, it is important for researchers to be able to self-reflect on their successes, failures and development needs in order for them to build a successful research career.

Ability to identify correct partners

UAS researchers need to be capable of justifying and rationalizing collaboration efforts with different partners and stakeholders. This means they need to

be able to successfully identify those who would directly benefit from their research but also those who may be indirectly interested. Networking and being active in different events is vital for being aware of different partners and stakeholders.

Career stage needs to be considered

Researcher career stages were also identified as being highly important in ensuring the development of different researchers. It was suggested that more senior researchers should have a responsibility to ensure the inclusion of earlier career researchers to help them build up their networks, experience, publications and overall reliability in the eyes of researcher teams and stakeholders. In regard to different research teams, research team leaders need to be competent in making sure there is a balance between different types of researchers. Mentoring was also mentioned as an important duty of more senior researchers. For UAS researchers, the importance of the development of the entire research team was heavily promoted.

Active in research field

Overall activity in the relevant research field and/or industry was also highlighted. Continued and persistent experience in these suggests that the researcher has an up-to-date understanding of the different needs and issues within that field and/or industry and also a deep understanding of relevant networks and partners.

Close collaboration with stakeholders

As mentioned in the previous section, deep collaboration skills were also highlighted in the interviews. This means that stakeholders should be an integral part of the applied research and they should be as deeply included in the research as possible. This means that the researchers need to be active in designing the research around their stakeholder and also being flexible to their time limitations and restrictions whenever possible. It also requires a certain level of communication skills which allows for such close collaboration to be executed successfully.

Able to utilize multi-, inter-, transdisciplinary approaches

Similar to the above the level of communication and soft skills which allows for multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary collaboration needs to be highlighted within UAS researchers. Working with members from different fields and industries means that researchers need to be able to adapt to the use of their own language appropriately and ensure others understand their opinions and ideas. It also requires a level of flexibility and willingness to understand different opinions and perspectives as well as trust in experts outside of their own field of research. It was suggested that researchers should be able to collaborate in multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary settings. Some also suggested that it was vital for researchers themselves to be specialists in their own area of research and the research team itself, to be multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary.

Able to lead and understand own career development

It was also identified that UAS researchers need to have a sense of accountability, motivation and willingness to enhance their own career development. It was highlighted that the more senior researchers become the more skills and experience they require and thus they need to be responsible enough to remain up-to-date and enhance their skills despite their senior level.

Collaborate and support research at organization

The importance of the research team and the research agenda of the UAS was highlighted in the interviews. It was considered that researchers should have a sense of partnership with their fellow researchers despite being from different teams and/or departments. Researchers should be willing to share their existing networks and support their colleagues, especially those from earlier career stages. Sharing information and research results amongst across departments and be willing to cooperate and include each other in research projects and funding applications.

Peer review skills

Providing high quality peer review was also considered as an important research skill. Peer reviewing and peer feedback are increasingly being incorporated into researcher assessments. However, it is vital that researchers understand how to provide objective feedback on their peers and the way it is delivered. It was identified that peer testimonials should play a key role in assessing the competence of researchers.

Aware of UAS researcher roles and duties

Another important aspect of UAS researchers is their ability to understand how the UAS researcher role differs from researcher roles at universities in general. It was considered important that those researchers with a university background should understand their unique roles and duties as UAS researchers. It is also vital for all researchers to recognize their skills and values and how this should be incorporated into the research team and the organization. However, it was also highlighted that researchers should be allowed to develop and grow their own research career and specialize in the areas they wish. Here it is vital to establish a balance between supporting the research team and research agenda of the organization, and ensuring the researcher can also establish their own research career.

Able to integrate education and research

As mentioned above, the ability to understand which aspects of the research can be incorporated into education and how an important skill is for UAS researchers. This may mean that researchers who do not have as much pedagogical experience should try to network and collaborate with lecturers as much as possible. UAS's should also help support this by organizing networking events between educational staff and researchers.

Other Important Themes

Defining innovation at HAMK

It is important for researchers to understand the research strategy and agenda of HAMK. It is also important to understand what innovation means to HAMK in order for researchers to incorporate this into their research plans.

Researchers need help in finding study unit collaboration

It is important for the UAS to support the collaboration of teaching staff and researchers. Networking and/or brainstorming events would be very beneficial.

Researcher evaluation should consider the unique profile of the researcher

Researcher evaluation and assessment should aim to base the evaluation on the progress made by individual researchers as opposed to having pre-measured limits, targets and/or metrics. Accomplishments will vary depending upon the research field, the type of research project and the field or industry in question.

Researcher mentors are needed

As there is no concrete manual on the role or duties of UAS researchers having senior research staff act as mentors to newly appointed or early career research staff would be very beneficial. This will also ensure that the specialists' skills and knowledge sets acquired will continue to exist within HAMK even if researchers leave, retire etc.

How to measure economic benefits and impact

Some of the research fields such as for those whose partners are primary from the public sector, measuring economic benefits and/or impact is not as straightforward. Whilst economic benefit is important, it is vital to also consider other forms of impact which are relevant to other fields dealing with the public sector in particular.

Need to build a research-based community in HAMK

It is important to develop a research-based community where peers will actively seek help and support from each other and also willingly provide it to others. It means being able to engage with experts from different departments and also sharing networks and partners. Research should be driven by a joint motivation to enhance the research profile and expertise of the UAS, in this case HAMK.

More collaboration amongst the public and private sector

It was suggested that the public sector may be able to benefit from solutions created in the private sector and vice versa. Whilst often the agenda of the research or the nature of the issue differs, solutions to different kinds of problems may sometimes be found from the same research. More active collaboration between these departments and research teams may be very beneficial.

Smaller projects could be dedicated to innovative work

As mentioned previously, innovation is to a certain extent restricted within UAS due to the nature of their funding and the responsibility they have to actual stakeholders. It was suggested that smaller projects could be dedicated into innovative thinking and design to help manage the risk factor. Experienced successes can thereafter be incorporated into larger projects.

Importance in timing evaluations

It is important to ensure that researchers do not become overwhelmed with evaluations and assessments. It is vital that researchers understand when evaluation will occur and the nature of these evaluations. It is also helpful to time evaluations by discussing the timetable for the researcher as well. Further understanding on when the most crucial times for conducting researcher evaluations is needed.

Workshops

Workshop 1

Methodology

The first workshop was conducted in March 2025 with the aim of gaining a fuller understanding of the research agenda at HAMK and the researcher roles and duties of Principal Research Scientists. The results of the survey were presented to the decision makers at HAMK and other relevant personnel, after which we discussed how the results reflect the above-mentioned aspects. The workshop was 1.5 hours in which we brainstormed together and defined the qualities, skills and expertise which HAMK Principal Research Scientists need.

Data

Personnel present:

- Vice Rector
- Research Director
- HR manager
- HR specialist
- HR project specialist
- Project manager

Findings

The findings below indicate some of the main skills and attributes which are expected from PRS at HAMK. These were used in the interviews to help guide the questions but also to help further analyze the findings of the interviews. An overview of these skills can be found in the diagram below:

Workshop 2

Methodology

The second workshop was conducted in April 2025. At this workshop personnel were invited to look at the first draft of qualitative criteria which had been developed form the fieldwork

findings. The personnel were also split into three separate groups where each group had to discuss and brainstorm solutions to three different themes. The results were used to help draft the second version of the qualitative criteria.

The questions discussed can be found below:

Theme 1. Research Career Stage

1. How do you think the different researcher career stages could be **objectively** defined (example years active in field, years since PhD graduation, amount of research produced etc.)?

- Early Career Researchers
- Mid-Career Researchers
- Late-Career Researchers

2. In which of the criteria does the impact of ‘researcher career stage’ need to be considered?

3. In relation to the criteria, you have chosen in question 2. How would you set the expectations for each career stage?

Theme 2. Researcher role in publications, funding applications and development projects.

1. How does the ‘role’ of the researcher impact the overall assessment of research publications, development projects and funding applications?

2. In each of these three criteria, to what extent is ‘role variance’ important?

3. In each of these three criteria, to what extent is a ‘leading role’ important?

Theme 3. Utilizing self-assessment and self-reflection.

1. Which criteria can be assessed using ‘self-assessment or self-reflection?’

2. What methods or precautions should be considered in the use of ‘self-assessment or self-reflection’ to help increase objectivity?

3. To what extent do you think ‘self-assessment or self-reflection’ can support responsible, ethical and fair evaluation?

Data

Personnel present:

- Dean
- Research Director

- Leading Research Scientist
- Researcher Evaluation Team Member
- Research Unit Director
- Publications Specialist
- Head of Library and Information Services
- Senior Specialist in International Research, Development and Innovation

Findings

Theme 1: Question 1

How early, mid and senior researchers are defined still unclear.

Do we categories them based upon the education they have received (PhD, Post-Doc, 10 years + research).

Or do we base it upon what has actually been achieved (late career is securing high profile funding from sources e.g.)

Do we need to consider other work experience as also being relevant to the researcher early, mid, senior stage?

Can EU definitions help this understanding?

miro

Theme 1: Question 2

Researcher career stage needs to be considered in various criteria

But description of the researcher and their duties (potentially different pathways) needs to be defined.

miro

Theme 1: Question 3

The limits and expectations for E,M and S researcher unclear

On one hand leadership experience may not be expected from ECR, but some ECR may have this form of experience from previous work experience.

Similarly, senior researchers may have less leadership experience due to being focused on research

Should senior researchers have something practical achievements to demonstrate? Regardless of years active?

Should the expectations be limited to pure research?

miro

Theme 2: Question 1

Researcher role should be highlighted giving a clear explanation for how the order of authors has been organized.

The role researchers have played is also vital for funding applications.

Collaboration is desirable and therefore different collaborations are positive.

Sole authorship is also important and the career stage and role of the researcher being hired needs to be considered

miro

Theme 2: Question 2

Variation of role equates to variation in skills and team work.

Variation in journals and applications is also desirable

Variation in publication type (also non-academic) is also important.

Ability to write for different audiences is important

role of the researcher and job description are important considerations

miro

Theme 2: Question 3

leading roles

Theme 3: Question 1

Self-assessment is important in evaluating soft skills (skills which are otherwise difficult to measure)

self-assessment should highlight different skills depending on the career path in question.

miro

Theme 3: Question 2

self-assessment
needs to be
guided by
supervisor or
peer review

self-assessment
needs to be
guided by
supervisor or
peer review

in the recruitment
phase, self-
assessment could be
used by the applicant
and the strengths and
weaknesses backed up
by the CV

RUN EU+ self-
assessment
tool could
help guide
this

miro

Theme 3: Question 3

Clear criteria
and anchors in
the self-
assessment to
help researcher

Systematic
approach will
help objectivity
and
comparability.

Should
not be
too heavy

Self-assessment
can be used as a
guide for
recruitment
interviews

miro

The findings from the second workshop provided insight into some of the aspects which still need to be clarified to help establish the new assessment process. These are aspects which need to be further discussed as the new evaluation frameworks are being developed.

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